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Non-philosophy and Laruelle's From Decision to Heresy

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With *Principles of Non-Philosophy*, Laruelle elaborates on the concepts and methods of non-philosophy with even greater attention. Yet he carries out this elaboration without much mention or textual analysis of the history of philosophy one sees in *Philosophies of Difference*. This is in part because *Principles of Non-Philosophy* aims to elaborate the very project it is detailing without any distance between that elaboration and the project itself. It is wildly constructivist and undeniably rooted in the history of the European philosophical tradition.

The idea for which he is best known is the “non-philosophy” of the title; a concept that initially manages to sound both appealing and a bit dubious. For the continental or interdisciplinary thinker, the alternative mode of approach is attractive, and being a non-thing has potential as a poetic claim, but Laruelle has set up a harder road in defining himself in comparison to philosophy, since in doing so he has to define all of philosophy as sharing characteristics that he avoids.

So what is non-philosophy? Simply put, to engage in non-philosophy (sometimes called “non-standard philosophy”) is to understand ideas not as the observations of privileged or transcendent perspectives, but as simply another part of what exists. Non-philosophy proclaims the impossibility of explaining the Real, and instead aims for smaller projects.

So what is non-philosophy? Simply put, to engage in non-philosophy (sometimes called “non-standard philosophy”) is to understand ideas not as the observations of privileged or transcendent perspectives, but as simply another part of what exists. Non-philosophy proclaims the impossibility of explaining the Real, and instead aims for smaller projects.

“Ray Brassier’s nihilism is closer to the option I wish to defend, in so far as it seems to me to be a once anti-correlationist and anti-subjectalist. My disagreement with his important and impressive book (*Nihil Unbound*) lies in the fact that I still cannot see how Laruelle’s non-philosophy, which seems essential to Brassier, allows him to obtain such an outcome. If it is explained to me that this is not his intention (since materialism and anti-materialism are ‘still philosophies’), then I must refuse this non-philosophy; because, to my mind, there is no other possibility today than to be

either a materialist or an anti-materialist (whether in the correlationist or subjectalist form) – every surpassing of this alternative is illusory...” (7).

Now if we remember, Ray Brassier in his *Nihil Unbound* argues that Laruelle’s attempt to homogenise all past and future philosophy into the single fundamental paradigm designated under the philosophical rubric of Decisionism. In which Laruelle privileges the Kantian problematic as the structure that underlies all philosophical thought – in Brassier’s words: “every philosophical Decision recapitulates the formal structure of a transcendental deduction... [the transcendental method] represents a methodological invariant for philosophy both before and after Kant.” (2007: 123; 2001: 120) For Brassier this is a “gratuitous assumption”: “Laruelle can simply drop the exorbitant claim that his account of decision is a description of philosophy tout court” (2007: 134) – rather, it is an account of ‘correlationism’.

Brassier also attacks Laruelle’s identification of the Real as One or Vision-in-One or One-in-One (in Laruelle’s convoluted terminology) with the apparently newly discovered transcendental subject Laruelle calls ‘Man’. This identification, Brassier argues, not only reinstates anthropocentrism – it does so in a manner hard to distinguish from solipsism.

Yet, Brassier, with the above qualifications still believes that the non-philosophical concept of Decision benefits a Meillassouxian critique of correlationism. Brassier discovers in his analysis of correlationist Decisionism that it is based on three specific structural forms of sense datum: 1) a conditioned datum – experience – which is ‘given’ to philosophical subjectivity, apparently from outside it; 2) this datum’s condition as a priori factum – for example, in the Kantian paradigm that Laruelle privileges, the categories as transcendental conditions of experience; and, 3) a synthetic unity wherein condition and conditioned are conjoined, which is in turn the condition of possibility of the contact between, and reciprocal relation of, datum and factum, transcendental and empirical. This is the transcendental binding of transcendental and empirical – the transcendental condition of transcendental thought, as radical immanence.

What Brassier rejects in Laruelle is his anthropocentric and solipsistic foreclosure within non-philosophy of an identity between the Real and non-philosophical thought itself. This is conceptual

idealism pure and simple. Yet, Brassier does believe that one can posit a relation between non-philosophical thought and the real that is unmediated by the philosophical Dyad of immanence and transcendence. Laruelle posits a non-Platonic Gnosticism in his *Struggle And Utopia At The End Times Of Philosophy* that resembles much of what Brassier is seeking in his use of the philosophical ‘cut’:

“Gnosis gives itself the World in a dogmatic way as an occasion, not comprehending the occasionality of the World in an immanent way, not bridging the genesis of occasionality. This is why we insist here on an immanence which is unable to be treated Platonistically or Platonically but practically by immanence itself. ... The instance of the gnostic or pure transcendental will not be blended with thought or alterity, in contrast to the non-philosophical transcendental. ... The transcendental needs an occasion but it does not imply a descent. Not only the Real but the transcendental remains separated. Yet within non-philosophy the transcendental also is not blended with the alterity of the World, cloning is precisely not a blending. It is thought which identifies itself in the Real-as-transcendental but the Real remains separated from thought” (249).⁵

Laruelle affirms a non-religious gnosis as a description of non-philosophy’s second stage (250, whatever that is? – need to uncover this). In this second stage of non-philosophy he tells us that “the primacy of science in the Real goes hand in hand with the transcendence that is partially reciprocal for the Real and philosophy, where the latter is still not really given-in-One, where real indifference is poorly distinguished from transcendental indifference, and immanent cloning is theoretically nonexistent” (250). Both Laruelle and Brassier will explicitly describe our knowledge of the Real in gnostic terms. Laruelle writes: “the gnosis of ‘matter’, the otherwise-than-materialist gnosis of the dispersive real, must be sought beyond materialism and the hyle.” (2001: 39) Or, elsewhere: “it is not a question of a secularization – still rational and transcendent – of an extraordinary experience, but of the possibility of rendering the usage of an exceptional or superhuman experience in every ‘ordinary man’ which was supposed to be refused to him. Philosophy is this organon, this a priori form which, giving us the World, forecloses the mystical experience which intrinsically constitutes humans...” (2009: 58) Finally Brassier: “Non-materialism reduces or suspends what Laruelle refers to as the ‘Greco-unitary’ epistemological paradigm and ascribes to it the status of an occasional material or empirical support for an anarchic or gnostic model of cognition.” (2001: 160) Attached to this remark is a footnote citing various works on historical gnosticism, including “Jonas’s classic study [Hans Jonas’ *The Gnostic*

Religion] [which] underlines gnosticism's profoundly anti-anthropocentric character as religion of an alien god.”

Yet, in *Nihil Unbound* Brassier argues that the Real that is philosophy's object is something with which we cannot have any form of relation whatsoever. For the Brassier of *Nihil Unbound*: “The real is less than nothing... The real is not the negation of being, since this would be to reconstitute it in opposition to something... Rather, it is immanently given as ‘being-nothing’” (137-138). The key to Brassier is not relation but non-relation, the “cut” or “separation” between thought and being, the Descision. The non-existence of consciousness – or, more precisely, the active being-nothing that is the destruction of consciousness, whether individual consciousness or species-consciousness – is a transcendental condition of consciousness. And this being-nothing of thought must be understood as something with which we cannot have a relation – whether as an authentic or an inauthentic relation to our own death, for instance – but as something altogether foreclosed to thought. This is what Brassier means when he says at the end of *Nihil Unbound*: “Extinction is real yet not empirical, since it is not of the order of experience. It is transcendental yet not ideal... In this regard, it is precisely the extinction of meaning that clears the way for the intelligibility of extinction...” (238).